

fore, be symptomatically directed against these two means of fatal terminations of the disease.

The following case, showing recovery from purulent streptococcic cerebrospinal meningitis, was offered: The patient, male, 22 years of age, had symptoms of rapidly increasing coma, neuro-muscular signs of meningitis, rigidity of neck, choked discs, and purulent otitis media and mastoiditis. Temperature, 102.5°; pulse, 40. Spinal fluid contained cocci in pairs and short chains, and pus. Decompression at once removed the mental symptoms. Mastoid operation, hypodermoclysis, enemata, saline solution by mouth, and solution of magnesium sulphate by mouth. On the seventh day following decompression, all signs of meningitis had disappeared. Patient died 188 days after the decompression operation, from toxemia caused by the repeated secondary infection of the decompression wound.

From this case the following conclusions are reached: "The combination of our experiences as otologists with the experience of the obstetrician makes the outlook for successful treatment of streptococcic meningitis appear much brighter than it has previously appeared. Oto-laryngologists should get as good results in cerebrospinal meningitis as the obstetrician obtains with puerperal sepsis cases. Although the surgeon can readily protect the patient from death by intra-cranial pressure, the management of the sepsis is quite another problem. This problem of sepsis has received more attention from the obstetrician than from any other medical group or specialty. The treatment should be focused on decompression, local and systemic drainage, administration of magnesium sulphate, and stimulating general hygiene."

Observation of Nystagmus Through the Closed Eyelids. DR. EDMUND PRINCE FOWLER, New York City.

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DISCUSSION.

DR. ARTHUR B. DUEL thought Dr. Fowler had presented a very ingenious method of making permanent records of ocular phenomena in vestibular nystagmus. He did not think such observations necessary to diagnosis, but when the apparatus was perfected the records, for those who understood them, would be useful in reporting cases. The tracings of nystagmus would leave no doubt of its presence. When one must depend upon the house-staff to report cases that arrived during one's absence, these tracings could be made and put into the records for subsequent study.

DR. FOWLER, in closing the discussion, said patients did not notice as much vertigo with rotation or following caloric reactions with the eyelids closed as they did with them open. For instance, one could produce nystagmic movements of the eyes with caloric stimulations and stop before the vertigo came on. Irrigation usually makes patients deathly ill and it surely is a great advantage to be able to avoid this annoying feature of the labyrinth tests. In many neurasthenics the rotation tests show nothing on account of the incessant blinking and rolling of the eyes around and about. If the lids are closed some approximation of the duration of the nystagmus may be ascertained.